

Table S3: Loadings obtained from the Principal Component Analysis on the 19 morphometric variables obtained from the *Teretrurus* samples after size correction using the residuals from a least-squares regression of the trait variable against SVL. Bold values indicate strong loading with correlation > 0.3.

Character	Description	PC1	PC2	PC3
Standard deviation		2.997	1.759	1.130
Proportion of Variance		0.472	0.162	0.067
Cumulative Proportion		0.472	0.635	0.703
Eigen values		8.985	3.095	1.278
HL	Head length	0.294	-0.004	0.079
HW	Head width	0.270	-0.045	-0.005
RL	Rostral length	0.156	0.147	0.484
ED	Eye diameter	0.242	0.180	0.143
OL	Ocular length	0.305	0.005	0.039
IOD	Inter-orbital distance	0.257	-0.202	0.061
IND	Inter-nares distance	0.270	0.092	0.111
SL	Snout length	0.279	-0.168	0.079
FL	Frontal length	0.215	-0.167	0.163
FW	Frontal width	0.162	-0.373	-0.189
PL	Parietal length	0.273	-0.066	-0.136
PW	Parietal width	0.223	-0.156	-0.174
IPS	Inter-parietal suture	0.236	0.245	-0.151
PFL	Prefrontal length	-0.068	-0.517	0.040
PFW	Prefrontal width	0.236	-0.069	-0.022
IPFS	Inter-prefrontal suture length	0.001	-0.512	-0.057
NL	Nasal length	0.256	0.222	-0.226
NW	Nasal width	0.249	0.092	0.117
INS	Inter-nasal suture length	0.095	0.133	-0.715